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RESEARCH-ARTICLE

Instruct me! Comparing Virtual Agents and Static Picture Instructions in Therapeutic Virtual Reality Exercises

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Instruct me! Comparing Virtual Agents and Static Picture Instructions in Therapeutic Virtual Reality Exercises

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Figure 1: The two instructional conditions in the VR-based therapy: (left) Virtual Agent guidance and (right) static picture-text instructions.

Abstract

Virtual reality (VR) systems enriched with virtual agents (VAs) present a promising approach for enhancing home-based rehabilitation for patients with vestibular disorders such as Benign Paroxysmal Positional Vertigo (BPPV) since therapeutic applications often consist of quite complex three-dimensional body movements. As a first test towards this goal, we conducted a 2x2 study design to investigate the impact of VA-guided instruction on the precision and user experience of therapeutic exercise execution compared to static instructions combining picture and text. Using the Meta Quest 3 VR headset, healthy participants performed two standard BPPV exercises ((i) the Sémont maneuver and (ii) the Brandt-Daroff exercise) under two conditions ((1) step-by-step demonstrations provided by a VA and (2) static picture-text guidance). The results indicate that there are no significant differences in movement accuracy between the VA and picture-text conditions, nor in the perceived workload. However, participants reported a clear preference for the VA condition, highlighting its enhanced comprehensibility, greater

engagement, and more intuitive and immersive learning experience. Notably, scores for perspicuity and novelty were significantly higher for the VA condition, indicating that participants found the VA instructions easier to understand and more innovative. In addition, the results revealed significantly fewer simulator sickness symptoms in the VA condition compared to the static picture-text condition. Our findings suggest that VA-guided instruction in VR enhances user experience and engagement, potentially improving therapy adherence in the future.

CCS Concepts

• **Human-centered computing** → **Virtual reality**; User studies.

Keywords

Virtual Agents, Virtual Reality, Head-Mounted Display, Instructional Design, Multimodal Interaction, Home-Based Rehabilitation, Therapeutic Exercises, Vertigo, Motion Tracking

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1 Introduction

Therapeutic exercises are essential for managing vestibular disorders, such as Benign Paroxysmal Positional Vertigo (BPPV), where precise execution of movements can significantly reduce symptoms of vertigo. Incorrect movements, however, can worsen symptoms rather than aid recovery [10]. A common form of guidance for these exercises is through written instructions, yet such methods often leave room for misinterpretation, which can result in ineffective motions [37].

Virtual Reality (VR) technology provides promising alternatives for home-based rehabilitation. VR headsets like the Meta Quest [27] enable home-based therapy through engaging, interactive guidance, reducing the need for clinical visits [11]. In this context, digital entities called Virtual Agents (VAs), capable of simulating human-like interaction, can serve as immersive, step-by-step instructors within VR environments [18]. This approach may offer a more engaging and effective rehabilitation experience, encouraging therapy adherence and improving long-term outcomes [48].

In an initial usability study, we compare VA-based guidance to static picture-text instructions for vestibular rehabilitation exercises in VR in terms of user experience, social presence, simulator sickness, workload, and user preference. Using a within-subject design and the Meta Quest platform, participants performed two therapeutic exercises under both instructional conditions. Motion tracking was employed to determine exercise accuracy by measuring deviations in head angles and positions from a reference. Additionally, user feedback was gathered to assess perceived usability. Healthy participants were chosen to evaluate instruction methods without VR-induced health risks for actual patients, as the goal of this study was mainly to test the feasibility of this approach. We aimed to identify needs for improvement in the user experience of the application, to evaluate it with real patients in future work, once the feasibility and safety of the application is ensured.

2 Related Work

To explore different design considerations for VR-based therapeutic exercises and instructional approaches, it is necessary to evaluate existing research in this field. This section highlights related work on vestibular rehabilitation, the role of VR in therapeutic applications, the use of VAs for guidance and a comparison of different instructional modalities.

2.1 Benign Paroxysmal Positional Vertigo

2.1.1 Prevalence of BPPV. Hanley et al. [15] describe benign paroxysmal positional vertigo (BPPV) as a prevalent cause of vertigo, characterized by brief but intense episodes of dizziness triggered by specific head movements. They report that BPPV can result from viral meningitis, trauma, or post-surgical procedures, estimating its prevalence at approximately 0.64 per 1,000 individuals. However, they suggest that the actual prevalence may be higher due to under-reporting, and emphasize that females are affected at approximately twice the rate of males.

2.1.2 Conventional Treatment Methods. In order to address the symptoms of BPPV, it is recommended that therapeutic maneuvers are employed, such as the Brandt-Daroff exercise [15] or the Sémont

maneuver [12]. The exercises comprise a series of repeated lateral movements of the head in an upward direction at a specific angle, held until the vertigo subsides. This process should be repeated multiple times per day [15]. While the efficacy of these exercises and techniques has been demonstrated, health professionals highlight the necessity of expert guidance and supervision [10]. Patients may struggle to execute exercises accurately at home, which can reduce therapeutic effectiveness and, in some cases, worsen symptoms. VR offers a promising solution by guiding and motivating patients in home-based therapy. Another advantage of VR might be the integration of eye-tracking technology in current HMDs. BPPV can often be diagnosed by observing nystagmus during certain movements [8], including those similar to the maneuvers explained before. The combination of precisely tracked exercises, as well as eye tracking could therefore be beneficial for diagnosis, therapy, and monitoring.

2.2 VR in Therapeutic Applications

2.2.1 Advantages and Challenges of VR. Recent advancements have made VR more accessible with lighter, more affordable devices [30]. Therefore, VR has become increasingly feasible for a wide range of applications, including therapeutic [45] and educational domains [23]. The immersive and interactive nature of VR creates engaging environments that encourage user involvement [41, 45] and can enhance both motivation and learning during exercises [34, 38, 47]. Yet, VR also poses challenges, such as user familiarization [23] and simulator sickness [17, 30], which can be reduced through rest periods [17].

2.2.2 VR-Supported Therapeutic Exercises. In therapeutic exercises, VR has demonstrated clear advantages, such as enabling patients to perform exercises from home [30, 45] and incorporating real-time monitoring to quantify the patient's progress [45]. Studies also indicate that task guidance in VR can reduce errors in exercise execution [41], while feedback mechanisms can further improve accuracy and efficiency [34]. Notably, VR has shown promise over traditional therapeutic methods. For instance, a study on VR-based mirror training [17] reported significant motor function improvements that exceeded those observed with traditional mirror training. Similarly, a study on children with cerebral palsy found that VR-based exercises led to better enjoyment, motivation, and increased movement control than conventional home exercises [4]. These findings imply that VR can improve therapy adherence and consistency, thereby supporting faster rehabilitation progress.

However, a major challenge in home-based therapy is the lack of real-time feedback. This has been addressed by Kinect-based motion tracking systems, resulting in significantly better movement accuracy [49]. When such real-time tools are absent, the efficiency of instructional methods becomes even more important.

2.3 Instructional Methods in VR

Today, technological assistance comes in a variety of forms. Auditory assistance devices, such as Apple's Siri or Amazon Alexa, text-based interfaces, video-based guidance systems, and numerous other technologies. The efficacy of different approaches varies according to the user's objectives and engagement requirements [22].

Different instructional methods should be carefully examined when developing guidance systems.

2.3.1 Instruction Modalities: Text, Audio, and Agents. Research has explored various instructional methods to identify the most suitable approaches for different contexts. Text-based instructions are generally more efficient than audio instructions, since reading takes less time [55]. Furthermore, written instructions tend to have a greater persuasive effect than auditory or visual formats [6].

VAs represent another instructional modality. Their ability to simulate human-like behavior [35] makes them promising tools across various domains [3]. Studies highlight their benefits in rehabilitation and exercise environments, where VAs provide real-time demonstrations and motivational feedback, outperforming static instructions such as illustrations or metal plates [5, 44]. VAs have also proven to be effective in educational settings, improving learning outcomes, knowledge acquisition, and increasing engagement [13, 20]. In healthcare, VAs can enhance patient education and therapy by providing tailored guidance [32, 40, 51] and they have been associated with improved health outcomes, motivation, and task adherence [3, 24, 43]. For example, VAs have been used to teach patients about diabetes and healthy eating in VR, significantly improving knowledge about this topic [54]. Especially in rehabilitation, VAs might improve traditional methods by providing dynamic visual demonstrations that encourage participation and promote proper execution.

However, preferences for VA interaction can differ. For example, Reicherts et al. [36] revealed a preference for verbal communication over written interactions with VAs as they were smoother, more flexible, required fewer modality shifts, and resulted in faster responses and increased user engagement. As a disadvantage, verbal instructions required immediate attention and could not be delayed, occasionally disrupting group conversation. In contrast, Tielman et al. [50] discovered that written instructions provided by VAs led to higher adherence than voice-based instructions.

The effectiveness of instructional modalities also depends on the context. VR-based learning has demonstrated several advantages over traditional methods, including greater flexibility in task design and improved safety [7]. Mansoori et al. [26] showed that VR-based serious games significantly enhanced medical students' performance compared to lecture-based teaching, highlighting the potential of VR to improve educational outcomes. Despite these advantages, some obstacles when employing VAs persist, particularly in VA design. To avoid the uncanny valley effect [1] and ensure user trust and acceptance, comprehensive usability testing and iterative design are required [56]. Moreover, the effectiveness of each modality depends on the task type: while animated agents are more suitable for motor and procedural learning, static annotations are more effective for navigation [22]. These findings imply that the suitability of different instructional modalities is strongly related to the complexity and nature of the task at hand.

2.3.2 Reading Challenges and Cognitive Load in VR. The selected instructional modality can also affect users' physical and cognitive well-being. Efficient readability requires high text legibility, which refers to the visual qualities of recognizing characters or symbols [19]. Limited resolution, motion blur, and visual artifacts, such as "fuzziness of text" [14], might diminish legibility in immersive

settings, lowering overall experience quality. Furthermore, reading in VR may cause oculomotor symptoms such as eye strain, impaired vision, or difficulty focusing, particularly if the visual design is inadequate [14, 19]. Therefore, tasks requiring prolonged focus on small text elements can increase visual effort and discomfort. These symptoms are major contributors to decreased performance and user experience in immersive environments [57].

3 Methods

Grounded on these findings and the acknowledged potentials of VA-supported VR rehabilitation, our work compares VA-instructed VR training with static picture-text instructions. Building on prior research, we propose the following hypotheses:

- **H1:** Participants report a better user experience when instructed by a virtual agent than when following picture-text instructions.
- **H2:** Participants experience stronger simulator sickness symptoms in the picture-text condition than in the virtual agent condition.
- **H3:** Participants report a higher perceived workload in the picture-text condition than in the virtual agent condition.
- **H4:** Participants perceive a stronger sense of social presence when instructed by a virtual agent than when following picture-text instructions.
- **H5:** Participants perform the exercises more accurately when instructed by a virtual agent than when following picture-text instructions.

To assess our hypotheses, a within-subject study was conducted, with participants performing two vestibular rehabilitation exercises under both conditions. The study measured movement accuracy, user experience, workload, simulator sickness, and social presence using standardized questionnaires and motion tracking data. Additionally, qualitative feedback was collected to understand participant's preferences. The following sections describe the study setup, application design, and evaluation methods.

3.1 User Study

A within-subject design was employed to compare two instructional methods for delivering therapeutic exercises in VR. Participants performed two standard BPPV exercises - the Sémont maneuver and the Brandt-Daroff exercise - under two experimental conditions:

- (1) VA-guided instructions, in which a virtual agent provided step-by-step demonstrations, and
- (2) static picture-text instructions displayed in VR.

Both conditions were administered using the same VR headset to control for hardware-related effects.

The Sémont maneuver is a rapid repositioning technique where the patient quickly moves from lying on one side to the other to dislodge otoliths from the semicircular canals [12]. The Brandt-Daroff exercise involves a series of controlled, repetitive movements in which the participant alternates between sitting upright and lying on one side, allowing gradual habituation and adaptation of the vestibular system [15].

A total of 30 participants were recruited through a university forum and personal networks. Eligibility required that participants be at least 18 years old and free of significant visual or medical

impairments that might hinder exercise execution or be exacerbated by VR. Since the study's primary objective was to compare instructional methods in terms of feasibility and user experience, it did not include patients with vertigo. BPPV exercises were chosen for their structured movements, which can be effectively tracked with a VR headset. Since VR can potentially induce symptoms of simulator sickness, direct patient use was not intended until the application itself was proven safe and usable.

According to the guidelines of our university, we filled out a basic questionnaire reflecting on potential ethical issues, which found that ethical approval is not mandatory in our case. To further reflect on ethical issues, we submitted our planned study to the ethics commission for a voluntary discussion. Here, we gathered valuable insights on the ethical implications of using IVAs, which we incorporated into our study design. At the beginning of the study, participants were informed about its purpose and procedure, and all provided informed consent. The sessions were conducted in living room-like environments, either at the university or in participants' homes, with exercises performed in a lying position on a sofa. Each session lasted approximately 30 minutes. They were randomly assigned to one of four counterbalanced groups to prevent potential biases. Each group completed a unique sequence combining the type of therapeutic maneuver (Sémont vs. Brandt-Daroff), the guidance method (agent vs. picture-text instructions) and the task order. Each maneuver was performed once per condition. For instance, one group first performed the Sémont maneuver guided by the VA, followed by the Brandt-Daroff exercise with picture-text instructions, while another group reversed this sequence. This counterbalancing ensured that all possible combinations of maneuver type, guidance method, and task order were evenly distributed among the participants, effectively mitigating learning effects.

After completing each condition, participants filled out a set of standardized questionnaires assessing various aspects of their experience, including user experience, workload, simulator sickness, and social presence (SP), as shown in Figure 2. These measurements provided quantitative insights into the effectiveness and usability of the different guidance methods. Additionally, open-ended questions were asked afterwards to complement the quantitative data with qualitative insights.

Figure 2: User Study Structure

3.2 Measurements

3.2.1 Questionnaires. Quantitative data was collected via four post-experience questionnaires. We used the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ) with a 7-point for user experience [21], which has six subscales: attractiveness, perspicuity, efficiency, dependability, stimulation, and novelty [21]. Further, we used the 21-point NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) for perceived workload [16], and a 7-point likert scale for the agent's social presence [2]. We also used the 4-point Simulator Sickness Questionnaire [42], with the dimensions nausea (N), oculomotor disturbance (O), and disorientation (D). The questionnaires were administered online in randomized order.

3.2.2 Performance Data. Additionally, motion tracking data from the VR headset was used to assess head position accuracy during the exercises. Performance was evaluated by comparing the average accuracy of the head positions between the agent-guided and picture-text-based instruction conditions.

3.2.3 Qualitative Data. To complement the quantitative measures, open-ended questions were integrated into the survey to capture participants' subjective experiences and preferences regarding the two instructional methods. After each condition, the participants were asked what they liked and what could be improved, and at the study's end, which method they preferred and why. These questions provided immediate feedback on the perceived strengths and potential shortcomings of both the VA and picture-text condition.

3.3 Application

The VR-based therapy application was developed using the Unity3D game engine (version 2022.3.50f1) [53], which served as the foundation for the scene sequences, VR integration, and the VA's behavior. External tools were utilized to create and refine animations, including character animations recorded with Qualisys Tracking Manager (QTM, version 2021.3) [33], voice output generated using Text-to-Speech software [25], and lip synchronization through the Oculus LipSync SDK [28]. The agent was modeled on the medical agent from the Intelligent Virtual Humans SDK [29], with additional hair and clothing from other agents.

The application was designed to run on the Meta Quest 3 headset, which also facilitated movement tracking during the study. The picture and text instruction cards for the picture-text condition were built in the collaborative design tool Figma [9].

3.3.1 Procedure of agent condition. First, the agent demonstrates the entire exercise while verbally explaining each step (using Voice A), as shown in Figure 3. Participants can replay the demonstration as many times as needed. When ready to start, the participant presses a button on the controller. During the actual execution of the exercise, auditory cues are provided in a different voice (Voice B), ensuring that the execution process is identical across both conditions and that the cues are not associated with the agent. At specific points in the exercise where patients with actual vertigo would normally hold a position until the dizziness subsides, participants in the study press a button to indicate they are in position. The system then tracks and records the accuracy of the head position for 30 seconds, with a timer displayed. This procedure is repeated for each relevant position in the exercise.

Figure 3: Agent Condition in VR

3.3.2 Procedure of picture-text condition. In the picture-text condition, participants are greeted with a textual introduction. They are then provided with a step-by-step picture guide, accompanied by text explanations, which they can navigate at their own pace and review as often as needed (see Figure 1, right). When participants feel ready to begin, they press a button to proceed. Similarly to the agent condition, auditory cues are provided in the same neutral voice (Voice B). The execution process, including pressing a button to confirm position and tracking for 30 seconds, is identical to the agent condition to ensure comparability.

4 Results

Our hypotheses predicted that the VA would report a better user experience (H1), fewer simulator sickness symptoms (H2), lower perceived workload (H3), stronger social presence (H4), and improved performance accuracy (H5) compared to the picture-text instructions. Although two different therapeutic exercises (Sémont and Brandt-Daroff) were used, our analysis focused solely on comparing the instructional methods (VA vs. pictures) and did not differentiate between the specific exercises performed.

A total of 30 participants (18 female, 12 male) took part in the study, predominantly aged 18–29. All participants reported either never using VR headsets or only very rarely.

Data preparation was performed in Excel, while statistical analyses and visualizations were conducted using RStudio (version 2024.09.1) [31]. An alpha level of 0.05 was applied for all statistical analyses to determine significance. All questionnaire results, their tests for normal distribution, as well as statistical comparisons between the conditions can be found in Table 1.

For the qualitative analysis, the open-ended responses were evaluated to identify recurring themes and key insights regarding participants’ experiences and preferences with the two instructional methods.

4.1 Questionnaires

4.1.1 User Experience Questionnaire. The UEQ assessed participants’ subjective experience of the two instructional methods. Data was analyzed using the publicly available Excel sheet, which also enables a benchmark comparison [52]. Figure 4 presents the mean values for the VA-based and picture-text instructions. The VA received higher ratings across most dimensions, with notable differences in perspicuity and novelty.

Figure 4: Comparison of UEQ scale means (and SE) between the VA-based and picture-text instructions

Participants rated the VA-based instructions as clearer and easier to understand (perspicuity) [46] ($M = 1.88, SD = 1.06$) compared to picture-text instructions ($M = 1.10, SD = 1.25, p = 0.0123$). The novelty of the VA was rated higher as well ($M = 0.91, SD = 0.98$ for agent condition vs. $M = 0.38, SD = 1.24$ for picture-text condition, $p = 0.0488$). Other factors did not show any significant differences.

4.1.2 Simulator Sickness Questionnaire. The SSQ measured simulator sickness symptoms [42] experienced by participants in each condition. The agent condition had a lower mean SSQ score ($M = 19.32, SD = 19.79$) than the picture-text condition ($M = 26.55, SD = 27.59$). Normality testing showed non-normal distributions, so a Wilcoxon signed-rank test was conducted. Results indicated a significant difference between the agent and picture-text conditions for the total score ($V = 244, p = 0.0293$) with a moderate effect size ($r = 0.5247$) (See Figure 5).

Figure 5: Comparison of SSQ dimension means (and SE) between the VA-based and picture-text instructions

Table 1: Descriptive and Inferential statistics for the Agent and Picture-Text conditions

Factor	Mean		SD		Shapiro-Wilk p		Test (Statistic)	p (Effect Size)
	Agent	Picture	Agent	Picture	Agent	Picture		
UEQ								
Attractiveness	0.63	0.65	0.98	0.84	.5221	.4710	t-test ($t(29) = -0.09$)	.929 ($d = .02$)
Perspicuity	1.88	1.10	1.06	1.25	.0034	.0264	Wilcoxon ($V = 63$)	.004 ($r = .54$)
Efficiency	0.85	0.58	0.82	0.86	.1476	.3674	t-test ($t(29) = 1.22$)	.233 ($d = -.22$)
Dependability	1.39	1.20	0.81	0.82	.0237	.1138	Wilcoxon ($V = 123$)	.185 ($r = .26$)
Stimulation	0.41	0.18	0.96	1.03	.6634	.6781	t-test ($t(29) = 1.13$)	.267 ($d = -.21$)
Novelty	0.91	0.38	0.98	1.24	.5773	.4401	t-test ($t(29) = 2.06$)	.049 ($d = -.38$)
SSQ								
Total Score	19.32	26.55	19.79	27.59	.0002	.0003	Wilcoxon ($V = 188.5$)	.0455 ($r = .42$)
Nausea (N)	6.04	8.59	9.54	13.57	.0000	.0000	Wilcoxon ($V = 37.5$)	.326 ($r = .14$)
Oculomotor (O)	19.71	27.04	18.42	26.23	.0048	.0027	Wilcoxon ($V = 154$)	.069 ($r = .38$)
Disorientation (D)	26.91	36.66	31.64	40.79	.0000	.0001	Wilcoxon ($V = 157.5$)	.051 ($r = .36$)
NASA-TLX	27.92	27.42	13.95	16.94	.0852	.0780	t-test ($t(29) = 0.14$)	.891 ($d = -.03$)
Social Presence	-4.27	-5.00	5.41	6.13	.4870	.0161	Wilcoxon ($V = 171.5$)	.324 ($r = .37$)
Rotation Deviation	86.40	87.10	3.74	4.24	.0013	.0012	Wilcoxon ($V = 268$)	.477 ($r = .58$)

4.1.3 NASA Task Load Index. The NASA-TLX assessed perceived workload, including mental and physical demand, and effort [16]. Scores were computed as the mean of all six questionnaire items. Normality testing showed that results for both the agent ($p = 0.0852$) and picture-text condition ($p = 0.0780$) were normally distributed. A paired t-test found no significant difference between both conditions.

4.1.4 Social Presence Questionnaire. The Social Presence Questionnaire measured participants' perception of the VA's social presence, including perceived co-presence and emotional engagement [2]. Scores were adjusted for consistency in scale direction. Normality testing showed that the agent instructions ($p = 0.487$) were normally distributed, while the picture-text instructions ($p = 0.016$) were not. A Wilcoxon signed-rank test found no significant difference between conditions.

4.2 Performance Accuracy

VR motion tracking data was analyzed to compare the accuracy of participants' head rotation in the exercise. Accuracy was quantified by measuring deviations from the optimal execution, established through a preliminary test round in which researchers corrected each other's head positions along the x, y and z axes.

Head rotation values were standardized to a range of -180° to 180° . Any values exceeding 180° were adjusted by subtracting 360° . Deviation from the optimal execution was then calculated using the Euclidean distance formula:

$$d = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$$

This was applied to each tracked head position across all exercises, capturing the overall discrepancy between the performed and ideal head orientations. Each participant's mean deviation score

(in degrees) was computed for both conditions, representing their average error in achieving the correct head position.

Shapiro-Wilk tests confirmed non-normal distributions for both the agent ($M = 86.4$, $SD = 3.74$, $W = 0.81$, $p = 0.0013$) and the picture-text conditions ($M = 87.1$, $SD = 4.24$, $W = 0.80$, $p = 0.0012$). A Wilcoxon signed-rank test found no significant difference between the two conditions.

4.3 Qualitative Feedback

The open-ended survey responses were analyzed to understand participants' experiences, preferences, and suggestions for improving the instructional methods.

4.3.1 VA-based instructions. Results demonstrated a clear preference for the VA-based instructions, with 25 of 30 participants choosing this condition. They cited better visual comprehensibility, as it was easier to grasp the required movement motions by watching the VA perform them beforehand. The instructions were described as more intuitive, engaging, visually appealing, easier to remember and more personal (P3). Despite the overall positive evaluation, some disadvantages were mentioned. The most common complaint was that the instruction was too slow, which caused the instructions to feel needlessly drawn out. Furthermore, one participant (P14) noticed that the VA did not always precisely follow the communicated movement instructions, resulting in minor discrepancies in the demonstration. A few also noted that the agent's gaze did not align with the participant's position (P5, P17), which lessened the sense of personal engagement and the feeling of direct interaction.

4.3.2 Picture-Text instructions. Despite the picture-text condition being less preferred, some participants valued the ability to perform the exercises at a self-chosen pace (P6, P7, P9, P10). This allowed for the flexible repetition of certain steps, which was not possible in the agent-based condition, where missed information required

repeating the entire instruction sequence. Additionally, some stated that the images were very clear and simple to comprehend (P8, P15, P17, P24), which helped them feel in control of the learning process. However, the static instructions also had limitations. The volume of information presented at once, especially in exercises requiring multiple steps, left some participants feeling overwhelmed. Others criticized the text and image size, finding them too small and therefore making it difficult to read and follow the instructions accurately. One participant (P20) explicitly expressed being confused about how and in what direction to rotate, as the instruction did not clarify that part enough.

5 Discussion

The objective of this study was to evaluate whether instructions provided by a VA enhance participants' engagement, motivation, and accuracy in movement execution during therapeutic exercises in VR compared to traditional picture-text instructions. The quantitative results from questionnaire data (UEQ, SSQ, NASA-TLX, Social Presence Questionnaire) and objective motion tracking metrics provided nuanced insights into these hypotheses. Additionally, qualitative feedback from open-ended responses offered further context, highlighting participants' subjective experiences and preferences regarding the two instructional methods.

5.1 Questionnaires

5.1.1 User Experience Questionnaire. As hypothesized in H1, participants found it easier to familiarize themselves with the software and tasks in the Agent condition compared to the static picture-text instructions, as indicated by the perspicuity score. In addition, the VA was rated significantly higher in terms of novelty, suggesting that participants found it more creative and interesting. However, no significant differences were observed for attractiveness, efficiency, dependability or stimulation, suggesting that although the VA improved clarity and was perceived as a novel approach, it did not lead to an overall increase in the UEQ scores. The UEQ scores for both conditions were generally moderate, suggesting that there is considerable room for improvement in the user experience in both conditions.

5.1.2 Simulator Sickness Questionnaire. In line with H2, participants reported significantly more simulator sickness symptoms in the picture-text condition than in the agent condition, with the difference being most apparent in the SSQ's oculomotor and disorientation subscales. Previous studies indicate that reading in VR can cause visual discomfort when text legibility is reduced due to low resolution, motion blur, or visual artifacts [14, 19]. In our instance, hardware constraints resulted in rather low visual fidelity, which was also criticized by participants in their qualitative survey responses. Tasks that involve extended concentration on small, detail-rich items, such as text, are more prone to visual discomfort under such conditions. This can lead to increased oculomotor strain, which is a major contributor to simulator sickness [57]. In contrast, by providing a more embodied and multimodal type of instruction, the VA condition most likely reduced the need for persistent fixation and frequent refocusing. The incorporation of movement and verbal instruction may have reduced unnatural gaze shifts or sensory-visual conflicts, resulting in a more comfortable experience.

5.1.3 NASA Task Load Index. Contrary to H3, the NASA-TLX results demonstrated no significant differences in perceived workload between conditions. This finding suggests that, although the agent's instructions were perceived as clearer, they did not result in a reduction in perceived workload during execution. A potential explanation for this could be the relatively low complexity of the exercises, which may not have been sufficiently demanding to lead to differences in workload. This explanation is supported by the overall low NASA-TLX scores across both conditions. Prior literature found that additional visual information resulted in a higher cognitive and temporal demand compared to only a conversation with an IVA [54]. Therefore, if more complex exercises are shown to participants in future studies, the perceived workload should continue to remain as low as possible.

5.1.4 Social Presence Questionnaire. In contrast to H4, the results of the Social Presence Questionnaire did not show a statistically significant difference between the agent and picture-text conditions. It is possible that participants perceived the VA more as an immersive video than as a socially engaging entity. This could be attributed to the lack of interactivity, real-time feedback, and natural behaviors (e.g., eye movement) in the VA's design. This highlights the need for future VA designs to include more social cues, such as facial expressions or interactive capabilities (e.g., the ability to respond to user questions). Such improvements could enhance perceptions of social presence in therapeutic VR settings and may improve both understanding and accuracy.

5.2 Performance Accuracy

In contrast to H5, no significant difference in movement accuracy was observed between the agent and picture-text conditions. One potential explanation is that the VA did not result in a more profound understanding of the exercise. However, the higher clarity ratings in the VA condition challenge this assumption. An alternative explanation could be the overall simplicity of the tasks or their similarity between conditions. This is countered by the overall poor performance of all participants in both conditions with a deviation above 80 degrees. These large deviations indicate that many participants made significant errors in completing the tasks correctly. This suggests that neither instructional method was fully effective in ensuring precise movement execution. It should be noted that our participants were mostly younger university students. Future studies should also evaluate this setup with other user groups, in order to account for individual differences of other user groups. Another potentially influencing factor is the use of the VR headset itself, which may have made achieving the optimal head position more challenging in both conditions. This limitation underscores the importance of real-time feedback mechanisms.

5.3 Qualitative Feedback

The qualitative feedback revealed a clear preference for VA-based instructions due to their visual comprehensibility and interactive nature. Participants found it easier to grasp movements by observing the agent perform them, making the instructions more intuitive and engaging. The sense of personal interaction further contributed to their preference, aligning with research on social presence in virtual learning environments [13]. These findings are consistent

with previous research, showing that VAs can be an effective way of presenting physical exercises [5] or procedural tasks [39] while also improving the learning interaction experience and knowledge construction [13, 26].

Nevertheless, participants also appreciated certain aspects of the Picture-Text instructions, especially the ability to progress at their own pace and reread steps as needed, which was also found in related work [36]. However, issues such as small text size and unclear movement descriptions made the instructions difficult to follow. Furthermore, some participants found the amount of text-based information overwhelming.

These results suggest that a hybrid strategy – combining the adaptability of self-paced static instructions with the clarity and engagement of VAs – could optimize learning and following instructions. Enhancing movement instructions, adding replayable visual components, and giving users control over the demonstration pace could lead to a more successful system of instruction.

To determine the best strategies for providing VR-based therapeutic instructions, future research should examine individual learning preferences and different combinations of VR instructional methods. Since not every method of instruction, including VAs, is equally suitable for all users [50], it is important to consider the specific advantages and disadvantages of each method.

5.4 Limitations and Future Work

This study has some limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results, and we propose multiple improvements for future work.

First, the reference values for optimal head positioning were derived from the researcher's own exercise execution. Since the researchers are not trained therapists, the accuracy of these reference values cannot be fully guaranteed. Future studies should validate these values with expert input from physiotherapists or medical professionals to establish a more precise baseline for motion tracking analysis.

Second, the use of VR hardware introduced potential constraints for participants. The weight and fit of the headset limited movement for some users, and the restricted visibility of the real environment led to uncertainty when leaning back. Additionally, VR exposure may exacerbate dizziness, which could be problematic for patients with vestibular disorders. Therefore, it might not be suitable for people in the moment they experience vertigo, but it can be used as a tool to learn the exercise execution before symptoms of vertigo occur. Future research could also explore whether VR-based guidance is more suitable for therapeutic exercises that involve minimal head movement, such as knee or pelvic rehabilitation. Alternatively, mixed-reality approaches that allow users to remain aware of their physical surroundings could be investigated. In addition, in future work it needs to be evaluated how people with BPPV react to VR and to the exercises, both as a one-time treatment, or in the long-term. Our study only tested the application as a one-time experience with healthy participants. We did this for safety reasons, and to ensure a good feasibility and usability before engaging with the actual target group. This poses a limitation for the validity of our results, and an evaluation with the actual target users should be done after revising the application.

Third, some technical and instructional limitations may have affected the effectiveness of the virtual guidance. While participants rated the VA's instructions as clearer, this did not translate into improved movement accuracy. Graphical constraints, such as pixelated visuals and flickering in the VR environment, may have influenced engagement and immersion, particularly in a therapeutic context. If tested with real patients, enhancing graphical fidelity and refining the VA's presentation – such as adding alternative camera angles or graphical overlays – could improve instructional clarity and usability, and further help to reduce the chances of simulator sickness. Additionally, as wearing a VR headset naturally restricts head movement, this approach may be more effective for rehabilitation exercises that focus on other body parts rather than precise head positioning.

Despite these limitations, the feasibility of implementing VA-based guidance in therapeutic settings remains promising. The system successfully delivered clear instructions and minimized simulator sickness, suggesting that VR guidance could be a viable alternative to traditional instructional methods. Future studies should further explore how VR-based rehabilitation can be adapted to individual needs and which types of exercises benefit most from VAs.

6 Conclusion

Our initial usability study demonstrated that VAs can significantly improve instruction clarity and reduce simulator sickness in VR-based therapeutic exercises compared to static picture-text instructions. For these reasons, the majority of participants preferred the VA over the picture-text instructions. However, the enhanced clarity did not translate into measurable improvements in movement accuracy or reduced workload. Furthermore, the VA did not significantly increase perceived social presence, highlighting the need for a more engaging and realistic agent design to foster user interaction. Despite these limitations, the results indicate the potential of VAs in training contexts, where clear instructions, user comfort, and minimal simulator sickness are critical factors. To further improve performance outcomes, future research should explore enhanced interactivity and real-time feedback mechanisms during exercise execution. It is important to note that the potential of VAs extends beyond the scope of vertigo treatment, including rehabilitation and fitness training, which warrants further exploration in different therapeutic domains.

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